

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR IMPROVING THE MODERNIZED DIDACTIC PROVISION OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: The article examines the theoretical basis of improving the didactic support of the modernization of environmental education in the higher education system, the system and effectiveness of the improvement of the modernized didactic support of environmental education. Also, pedagogical conditions for improving the modernized didactic provision of environmental education in the higher education system were analyzed.

Key words: higher education, ecology, ecological education, ecological education, didactic, modernization, ecotheological, pedagogical, ecoethical, global, systematic analysis, pedagogical experiment, monitoring, adaptation, creative.

INTRODUCTION. Organization of integrated education is a prerequisite for improving the modernized didactic provision of environmental education in the modern conditions of the higher education system. At the same time, the effectiveness of this methodology depends on the organization of education on a correct and precise technological basis.

There are a number of reasons that increase the need to improve the modernized didactic provision of environmental education in the higher education system. This is a complex and complex process that is directly related to the formation of the moral attitude of mankind towards the environment, to stand in a position of high morality in the use of nature. As a result, students develop the qualities of preserving nature, making it more natural, creativity, creativity, more precisely, ecological moral competence acts as an inspiring, inspiring and encouraging tool for the development of such qualities.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. The issues of modernization of didactic support of environmental education are reflected in the scientific researches of classical period thinkers such as American and Western philosophers I. Kant, G. Hegel, I. G. Fichte, F. Schelling. Also I.L. Vershok, N.A. Sheyafetdinova, Y.A. Shishkina, YE.I. Balakina, E. Khoshimova, E. Karimova, Y. Shodimetov, S. Mamashokirov, E. Usmonov, H. Salomova, D. Rasilov, A. K.

Berdimuratova, S. It was analyzed in the studies of Sanginov, Sh.P. Makhmudov, A. Akhmedov, A. Koldoshev.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The technology of improving the modernized didactic support of environmental education in the higher education system was designed based on the conceptual foundations of the reflexive approach, and included the following stages with a goal-oriented, systematic description: analytical - knowledge of students' ecological and ethical competence, improvement of qualifications and skills and their assessment; organizational-preparation - clarification of the prospect of technology implementation, selection of forms, methods and tools of the pedagogical process, improvement of methodological training of professors and teachers; related to activity - step-by-step implementation of the technology of developing students' ecological and ethical competence; monitoring - assessment of the dynamics of development of students' ecological and ethical competence, making corrections to the pedagogical process when necessary; result - assessment of results and clarification of future tasks of educational work.

It consists of two technological parts: content-procedural and organizational-pedagogical.

The content of the technology reflects the unit of cognitive - practical activity - reflection and the levels of development of ecoethical competence (awareness, understanding, attitude and thinking) manifested in each of these stages in a unique way.

The development and implementation of educational projects in the organization of education and conducting practical training aimed at improving the modernized didactic provision of environmental education in the higher education system has a good effect. Through the development and implementation of educational projects, the skills of combating the negative effects of global environmental problems, preventing the social aggression of environmental problems, and rational use of nature will be included. It allows you to quickly understand various legislation, normative, legal and moral and ethical standards and behavior in improving the modernized didactic support of environmental education in the higher education system. In this way, they will have a wide opportunity to develop environmental education.

Preparation of projects requires students to work more independently. In this process, they rely on high ethical standards in dealing with environmental problems.

In order to complete the project, it is necessary to provide students with the following methodological recommendations: 1) clearly formulate the question for which the answer is sought in connection with modern environmental problems; 2) assess whether it is possible to come to a clear solution to the given issue from the point of view of your existing knowledge; 3) identify major and minor problems and seek answers to them; 4) if you have found an answer, formulate a solution based on the acquired knowledge; 5) put forward hypotheses based on the methods of induction or analogy; 6) compare the obtained results with the known ones; 7) check the accuracy of the logical methods used; 8) check the correctness of all generalizations and judgments used in finding a solution; 9) try to choose visible symbols of task objects; 10) form the result of the solution based on strict logic; 11) evaluate the received judgments by means of "for" and "against" judgments.

The improvement of the modernized didactic provision of environmental education in the higher education system was divided into several stages.

The first stage is a motivational reflexive stage, which must be consciously felt by the students of the need for knowledge and clearly indicate the goals and tasks. In this, students get acquainted with the main content of ecological activity, initiative and the concept of "Ecological worldview", and the science they are learning is synthesized. The first step of this stage is the motivation of learners. For this purpose, an environment was created for students to consciously understand environmental processes (videos about the environment, nature, crises).

The content of analytical pedagogical laboratories at this stage is that the design of life processes (life events that create life experience, process design, that is, educational dialogues between the teacher and the student, by bringing education closer to everyday life activities) formation of the studied material as the stages of the culture being created, the formation of one's own "I" through the realization of the values in life and the ability to enter into a balanced relationship with the environment) was carried out.

The second stage is reproductive and educational. Development of scientific ecological knowledge through practical experiences. The basis of the experience of scientific ecological knowledge further strengthens knowledge, skills and abilities and directs them to the level of competence. The process of mastering the algorithm for working with the project is aimed at developing creative activity and implementing the necessary environmental measures in a changing world. In the theoretical part of the design, the following are: identification of

the actual problem; choosing a topic for design; putting forward functional or ideological hypotheses; modeling; it was recommended to prepare and defend the presentation of the creative work.

The third stage is constructive. At this stage, students demonstrate their "methods". At the constructive stage, the socio-psychological world of the individual is illuminated.

The presented project will be creatively developed again. the topics may be different in a group of students, but the framework that forms the system is the same. This stage also consists of several parts, which are: • identification of actual problems of the studied aspect (through associative means, pictures, video tapes, texts, etc.), the scope and level of accuracy of the problem; • the process of studying the problem with information and acceleration through innovative educational technologies;• analysis and grouping of students' answers;• description of educational goals through a problem tree;• determination of the object and subject of project work, justification and proof of idea generation; • Formation of reflection and transformation of knowledge into axiological values was observed.

The fourth stage is the formation of the student's ecological outlook. The uniqueness of this stage is that the personality of the student begins to feel unity with the world in his worldview. At this stage, students will have the opportunity to apply vitagen, reflexive, information, communication, facilitation technologies and see the results of these technologies. During the implementation of the fourth stage, there is an opportunity to use mental maps, to summarize and understand the essence of knowledge, and to apply the acquired knowledge in life processes.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, in the environmental education of students and young people at the stages of higher education, the main focus is on global skills related to ecosystems and environmental protection, rational and economical use of nature, and the use of technologies aimed at improving the environment. importance is given. Also, attention is paid to issues related to sustainable development, knowledge of global and regional environmental problems. At the same time, the spiritual values of the Uzbek people, which are considered one of the main sources of ecological culture, are related to the protection, preservation, reproduction and transmission of values related to the preservation of nature, environment and cultural heritage to future generations. Qualities such as personal responsibility, conscientiousness, devotion to duty, determination, and initiative are formed and developed.

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